

MEDICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH ON MENTAL HEALTH OF FOREIGN STUDENTS IN OSH

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Abstract

In this era of competition, we find many students dealing with mental health issue.

So it's very important to discuss this aspect. So here we present you with complete story of students studying in OSH STATE UNIVERSITY dealing with their mental health issues.

We have discussed the problems these foreign students face during their academic journeys. While researching on it we need to keep in mind that we have to know the problem, recognise the problem and lastly most important ways to deal with the problem so that we could help the individual.

We conducted a survey among the students of Osh state University from the academic year 1st to 6th. In this article we will discuss the results of the survey, a report of the survey, problems of the students their mental health and solutions to their problems and we will discuss the importance of mental health.

Keywords: mental health, education, international students.

What is mental health?

It is the most common misconception of society that we consider health as a physical aspect, if we find a individual who is physically healthy, with no infections, no trauma, taking note that he /she is not having any serious or deadly disease we define them as healthy individuals.

But what is the definition of health?

How can we say someone is healthy?

What makes a person healthy?

WHO defines Health as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity.

Maintaining a positive mental health and treating any mental health conditions is crucial to stabilizing constructive behaviours, emotions, and thoughts. Focusing on mental health care can increase productivity, enhance our self-image, and improve relationships.

Other benefits of taking care of our mental health can include:

Improving our mood

Reducing our anxiety

Creating an enhanced sense of inner peace

Thinking more clearly

Improving our relationships

Increasing our self-esteem

Our mental health is something that impacts our eating and sleeping habits and has a lot to do with our physical health as well. It is important to address our

mental health needs, or oftentimes we will feel the impact of it in other areas of our health as well.

So it very important for us to discuss about students mental health.

Most of these students are foreign students coming from different countries,

Reports suggest that many students miss their homes, they feel home sick, they have to compromise with their food, leading them to lack of nutrition and eventually poor physical development, adapting to different language, different culture, different food different syllabus, different pattern of studies is real challenge for the students in their initials years to foreign land.

Sleep a power up for your mental health

In the survey we conducted we found 58.3 % of students are awake at nights and have a habit of sleeping late at nights. 10% completely agreed that they have problems with sleep, they lack sleep. 17 % agreed on lacking sleep occasionally. Which eventually impacts on their academics.

Sleep is very crucial for good health as diet and exercise. Good sleep improves your brain performance, mood, and health. Not getting enough quality sleep regularly raises the risk of many diseases and disorders. These range from heart disease and stroke to obesity and dementia.

Depression

Depression is a mental state of low mood and aversion to activity, which affects more than 280 million people of all ages (about 3.5% of the global population). Classified medically as a mental and behavioural disorder.

Adversity in childhood, such as bereavement, neglect, mental abuse, physical abuse, sexual abuse, or

unequal parental treatment of siblings can contribute to depression in adulthood.

19% individual feel depressed, 25% of students felt like they don't know what is their condition. 64% of students said they are not depressed at all.

Depression leads to lack of concentration

The students answered it in a mixed pattern

6) Are you facing a lack of concentration ?

- Completely agree [19]
- Somewhat agree [36]
- Neutral [68]
- Somewhat disagree [10]
- Completely disagree [24]

It takes usually a lot more time to do a work when you are mentally disturbed.

Our productivity depends on our mind-set and physical health. 15% agreed that it usually requires

more time for them to complete a task which otherwise they could have done in less time.

Below is a chart which gives an idea of overall responses by the students:

Inability to make a decision	12 % students face this problem 24 % agreed sometimes they are unable
Do they know why they depressed	17% yes 37% not sure
Irritated and angry	10% yes
Feel like they have no future	7% yes 50% no
Feeling of guilt	7% yes
Felt exhausted	6% yes
Sudden Weight gain or loss	15% experienced with this issue
Trouble in relations with friends, family etc..	15%
Addicted to phone	17%
Addicted to smoking or alcohol	3%
Addicted to social media	35 %
Discuss about their mental health	37%
Share their problems with	Parents 28% Friends 45% Teachers 0% No one 25%
Stressed about studies	48% yes
Suffering from panic attacks	14% yes
Make new friends	65% yes
Know how overcome depression	63%
Things they do to overcome depression	Listen music 32% Talk about it 14% Read books 4% Sit alone and cry 8% Go for a walk 18% Other 14%
Girls depressed during their bleeding phase of menstrual cycle	24%
On antidepressants	0%
Exercise	Daily 16% Sometimes 53%
Study well	13% yes 31 % may be

Here are some pie charts which gives us the idea about percentage of students agreeing and disagreeing on the situations

6) Are you facing a lack of concentration ?

11) Are you feeling, " You have no future ?"

13) Have you been feeling guilty for everything you do ?

- Completely agree [11]
- Somewhat agree [21]
- Neutral [47]
- Somewhat disagree [23]
- Completely disagree [54]

29) What do you do to cop up with the depression ?

- Listen music [49]
- Talk with someone [32]
- Read books [7]
- Sit alone and cry [13]
- Go for a walk [28]
- other [21]

30) If you are a girl , do you feel more depressed during bleeding

Why is dealing with depression so difficult?

Depression drains your energy, hope, and drive, making it difficult to take the steps that will help you to feel better. Sometimes, just thinking about the things you should do to feel better, like exercising or spending time with friends, can seem exhausting or impossible to put into action.

The things that help the most are the things that are the most difficult to do. There is a big difference, however, between something that's difficult and something that's impossible. While recovering from depression isn't quick or easy, you do have more control than you

realize—even if your depression is severe and stubbornly persistent.

Taking the first step is always the hardest. But going for a walk or getting up and dancing to your favourite music, for example, is something you can do right now. And it can substantially boost your mood and energy for several hours—long enough to put a second recovery step into action, such as preparing a mood-boosting meal or arranging to meet an old friend. By taking the following small but positive steps day by day, you'll soon lift the heavy fog of depression and find yourself feeling happier, healthier, and more hopeful again.

12) Do you feel , Your life is sad , as there is no joy left in your life

Coping with depression tip 1: Reach out and stay connected

Getting support plays an essential role in overcoming depression. On your own, it can be difficult to maintain a healthy perspective and sustain the effort required to beat depression. At the same time, the very nature of depression makes it difficult to reach out for help. When you're depressed, the tendency is to withdraw and isolate so that connecting to even close family members and friends can be tough.

You may feel too exhausted to talk, ashamed at your situation, or guilty for neglecting certain relationships. But this is just the depression talking. Staying connected to other people and taking part in social activities will make a world of difference in your mood and outlook. Reaching out is not a sign of weakness and it won't mean you're a burden to others. Your loved ones care about you and want to help. And if you don't feel that you have anyone to turn to, it's never too late to build new friendships and improve your support network.

How to reach out for depression support

Look for support from people who make you feel safe and cared for. The person you talk to doesn't have to be able to fix you; they just need to be a good listener—someone who'll listen attentively and compassionately without being distracted or judging you.

Make face-time a priority. Phone calls, social media, and texting are great ways to stay in touch, but they don't replace good old-fashioned in-person quality time. The simple act of talking to someone face to face about how you feel can play a big role in relieving depression and keeping it away.

Try to keep up with social activities even if you don't feel like it. Often when you're depressed, it feels

more comfortable to retreat into your shell, but being around other people will make you feel less depressed.

Find ways to support others. It's nice to receive support, but research shows you get an even bigger mood boost from providing support yourself. So find ways—both big and small—to help others: volunteer, be a listening ear for a friend, do something nice for somebody.

Care for a pet. While nothing can replace the human connection, pets can bring joy and companionship into your life and help you feel less isolated. Caring for a pet can also get you outside of yourself and give you a sense of being needed—both powerful antidotes to depression.

Join a support group for depression. Being with others dealing with depression can go a long way in reducing your sense of isolation. You can also encourage each other, give and receive advice on how to cope, and share your experiences.

10 tips for staying connected

Talk to one person about your feelings.

Help someone else by volunteering.

Have lunch or coffee with a friend.

Ask a loved one to check in with you regularly.

Accompany someone to the movies, a concert, or a small get-together.

Call or email an old friend.

Go for a walk with a workout buddy.

Schedule a weekly dinner date.

Meet new people by taking a class or joining a club.

Confide in a clergy member, teacher, or sports coach.

Tip 2: Do things that make you feel good

In order to overcome depression, you have to do things that relax and energize you. This includes following a healthy lifestyle, learning how to better manage stress, setting limits on what you're able to do, and scheduling fun activities into your day.

Do things you enjoy (or used to)

While you can't force yourself to have fun or experience pleasure, you can push yourself to do things, even when you don't feel like it. You might be surprised at how much better you feel once you're out in the world. Even if your depression doesn't lift immediately, you'll gradually feel more upbeat and energetic as you make time for fun activities.

Pick up a former hobby or a sport you used to like. Express yourself creatively through music, art, or writing. Go out with friends. Take a day trip to a museum, the mountains, or the ballpark.

Support your health

Aim for eight hours of sleep. Depression typically involves sleep problems; whether you're sleeping too little or too much, your mood suffers. Get on a better sleep schedule by learning healthy sleep habits.

Keep stress in check. Not only does stress prolong and worsen depression, but it can also trigger it. Figure out all the things in your life that stress you out, such as work overload, money problems, or unsupportive relationships, and find ways to relieve the pressure and regain control.

Practice relaxation techniques. A daily relaxation practice can help relieve symptoms of depression, reduce stress, and boost feelings of joy and well-being. Try yoga, deep breathing, progressive muscle relaxation, or meditation.

Develop a "wellness toolbox" to deal with depression

Come up with a list of things that you can do for a quick mood boost. The more "tools" for coping with depression you have, the better. Try and implement a few of these ideas each day, even if you're feeling good.

- Spend some time in nature.
- List what you like about yourself.
- Read a good book.
- Watch a funny movie or TV show.
- Take a long, hot bath.
- Take care of a few small tasks.
- Play with a pet.
- Talk to friends or family face-to-face.
- Listen to music.
- Do something spontaneous.

Tip 3: Get moving

When you're depressed, just getting out of bed can seem like a daunting task, let alone working out! But exercise is a powerful depression fighter—and one of the most important tools in your recovery arsenal. Research shows that regular exercise can be as effective as medication for relieving depression symptoms. It also helps prevent relapse once you're well.

To get the most benefit, aim for at least 30 minutes of exercise per day. This doesn't have to be all at once—and it's okay to start small. A 10-minute walk can improve your mood for two hours.

Exercise is something you can do right now to boost your mood

Your fatigue will improve if you stick with it. Starting to exercise can be difficult when you're depressed and feeling exhausted. But research shows that your energy levels will improve if you keep with it. Exercise will help you to feel energized and less fatigued, not more.

Find exercises that are continuous and rhythmic. The most benefits for depression come from rhythmic exercise—such as walking, weight training, swimming, martial arts, or dancing—where you move both your arms and legs.

Add a mindfulness element, especially if your depression is rooted in unresolved trauma or fed by obsessive, negative thoughts. Focus on how your body feels as you move—such as the sensation of your feet hitting the ground, or the feeling of the wind on your skin, or the rhythm of your breathing.

Tip 4: Eat a healthy, depression-fighting diet

What you eat has a direct impact on the way you feel. Reduce your intake of foods that can adversely affect your brain and mood, such as caffeine, alcohol, trans fats, and foods with high levels of chemical preservatives or hormones (such as certain meats).

Don't skip meals. Going too long between meals can make you feel irritable and tired, so aim to eat something at least every three to four hours.

Minimize sugar and refined carbs. You may crave sugary snacks, baked goods, or comfort foods such as pasta or French fries, but these "feel-good" foods quickly lead to a crash in mood and energy. Aim to cut out as much of these foods as possible.

Boost your B vitamins. Deficiencies in B vitamins such as folic acid and B-12 can trigger depression. To get more, take a B-complex vitamin supplement or eat more citrus fruit, leafy greens, beans, chicken, and eggs.

Boost your mood with foods rich in omega-3 fatty acids. Omega-3 fatty acids play an essential role in stabilizing mood. The best sources are fatty fish such as salmon, herring, mackerel, anchovies, sardines, tuna, and some cold-water fish oil supplements.

Tip 5: Get a daily dose of sunlight

Sunlight can help boost serotonin levels and improve your mood. Whenever possible, get outside during daylight hours and expose yourself to the sun for at least 15 minutes a day. Remove sunglasses (but never stare directly at the sun) and use sunscreen as needed.

Take a walk on your lunch break, have your coffee outside, enjoy an al fresco meal, or spend time gardening.

Double up on the benefits of sunlight by exercising outside. Try hiking, walking in a local park, or playing golf or tennis with a friend.

Increase the amount of natural light in your home and workplace by opening blinds and drapes and sitting near windows.

If you live somewhere with little winter sunshine, try using a light therapy box.

Dealing with the winter blues

For some people, the reduced daylight hours of winter lead to a form of depression known as seasonal

affective disorder (SAD). SAD can make you feel like a completely different person to who you are in the summer: hopeless, sad, tense, or stressed, with no interest in friends or activities you normally love. No matter how hopeless you feel, though, there are plenty of things you can do to keep your mood stable throughout the year.

Tip 6: Challenge negative thinking

Do you feel like you're powerless or weak? That bad things happen and there's not much you can do about it? That your situation is hopeless? Depression puts a negative spin on everything, including the way you see yourself and your expectations for the future.

When these types of thoughts overwhelm you, it's important to remember that this is a symptom of your depression and these irrational, pessimistic attitudes—known as cognitive distortions—aren't realistic. When you really examine them they don't hold up. But even so, they can be tough to give up. You can't break out of this pessimistic mind frame by telling yourself to "just think positive." Often, it's part of a lifelong pattern of thinking that's become so automatic you're not even completely aware of it. Rather, the trick is to identify the type of negative thoughts that are fuelling your depression, and replace them with a more balanced way of thinking.

Conclusion

The aims of this study were to identify and evaluate the types of mental health of students. To analyse what are students going through, what they think, why are they depressed, how they overcome their problems and to know whom they look up for sharing their problems.

We now have an idea of their problems and we can help these students to come out through these difficult situations. Set guidelines for them and make a place where they can openly their problems and we can guide them and help them to excel in their academic.

References

1. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK262963>
2. https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/154543&ved=2ahUKEwiyscDS8_j7AhVLx-osKHa6zB84QFnoECAsQAQ&usg=AOvVaw2tAFODUA7UEE8a-jqfq9za
3. https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.health.harvard.edu/topics/mental-health&ved=2ahUKEwiyscDS8_j7AhVLx-osKHa6zB84QFnoECA0QAQ&usg=AOvVaw3fzKJF8OoTrXEJESp5gCjj
4. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j>

https://www.psycom.net/mental-health-wellbeing/top-25-mental-health-articles&ved=2ahUKEwiyscDS8_j7AhVLx-osKHa6zB84QFnoECDEQAQ&usg=AOvVaw0Fc6FPIDRIQ3VgxyXF473

5.

https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://ijmhs.biomedcentral.com/articles&ved=2ahUKEwiyscDS8_j7AhVLx-osKHa6zB84QFnoECCsQAQ&usg=AOvVaw0odDnY8MVS5qBw9M-KWnAo

6.

https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.cdc.gov/mentalhealth/learn/index.htm&ved=2ahUKEwiyscDS8_j7AhVLx-osKHa6zB84QFnoECDkQAQ&usg=AOvVaw0FLsh9aT6XXAmtE_1a4Z2a

7.

https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://scholar.google.com/scholar_url%3Furl%3Dhttps://www.academia.edu/download/46182950/Global_mental_health_1_-_No_health_witho20160602-18337-bj5tqc.pdf%26hl%3Den%26sa%3DX%26ei%3Dz6WZY8bwI8eTy9YPktqk-AE%26scisig%3DAAGBfm3BLfqmOmmN_KwHe0t8s68D_yz5Hw%26oi%3Dscholarr&ved=2ahUKEwiyscDS8_j7AhVLx-osKHa6zB84QgAN6BAgKEAI&usg=AOvVaw2ezQDGnynbV6XrpI2e4OSc

8.

https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://scholar.google.com/scholar_url%3Furl%3Dhttps://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4885556/%26hl%3Den%26sa%3DX%26ei%3DEd6ZY82NLR2Uy9YPqout4A4%26scisig%3DAAGBfm2Q5MRI5JWSmm2H0fTxsbfFXvnK2A%26oi%3Dscholarr&ved=2ahUKEwius_2lqfn7AhUQx-osKHdOCA0oQgAN6BAgPEAE&usg=AOvVaw3T0gvEmYKgJAePJCbXfJkn

9.

https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.sprc.org/collegesuniversities/consequences&ved=2ahUKEwius_2lqfn7AhUQxosKHdOCA0oQFnoECBAQAQ&usg=AOvVaw3yBtXKKGWuKDF-PmT62wx65

10.

https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.mind.org.uk/information-support/tips-for-everyday-living/student-life/about-student-mental-health/&ved=2ahUKEwius_2lqfn7AhUQxosKHdOCA0oQFnoECCMQAQ&usg=AOvVaw26x6fwaplKkCq7sq4jNs0v